

Enhancement and Restoration of Underwater Images

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Abstract—The aim of exploring the deep undersea world map, a picture of high quality without interfering objects is preferred. However, within the water, the image quality tends to be hampered by light scattering, water density, and light attenuation. effects. Besides, the dynamic interference may affect the important underwater map. during this paper, we proposed a multi-step and all-around underwater image processing system, especially for the underwater images taken in succession to enhance the image quality, remove the dynamic interference, and reconstruct the image. The first step involves utilizing the dark channel approach together with the improved gray world algorithm for brightness adaptation and color correction. Initially, it identifies and removes a dynamic interference regarding image enhancement. Secondly, we applied an upgraded total variation model to patch the blank at the value of resolution. Finally, the superresolution of the small print is realized by applying an improved BP network. After simulation and experiments, our system proved to realize ideal results of image enhancement and reconstruction.

Keywords— Undersea mapping, Underwater image processing, Light scattering, Water density, Light attenuation, Dynamic interference, Dark channel approach, Gray world algorithm, Total variation model, Super-resolution.

I. INTRODUCTION

The oceans are home to a variety of enigmatic and unidentified species as well as a vast supply of energy-producing resources, which contribute significantly to the sustainability of life on Earth [1]. Since the turn of the 20th century, high-tech maritime exploration initiatives have been undertaken globally [2]. Because of its ability to hold large amounts of data, vision technology has received a lot of attention [3]. In several undersea applications, including robotics [4], rescue operations, man-made structural inspection, ecological monitoring, tracking marine life [5], and real-time navigation systems [6], [7], researchers and scholars seek to obtain high-resolution underwater photographs. Academics and researchers are looking for high-resolution underwater photos. However, the underwater environment severely degrades image quality, causing problems that are easy to fix in terrestrial imaging. Images were taken underwater consistently exhibit color casts, such as green-bluish hues, which are brought on by varying degrees of red, blue, and green light attenuation. Particles in suspension also have Images with a lot of blur and haze are caused by the fact that submerged objects absorb most photon energy and shift the direction of light before it reaches the camera [8]. Artificial light sources are widely employed in underwater imaging to extend their effective range. However, scattering and absorption have an impact on artificial light [9]. Simultaneously, an uneven lighting pattern is applied, leading to luminous areas in the center of the underwater picture and inadequate lighting in the direction of the boards [10]. Shadowing is one of the other phenomena that degrade quality. For underwater photographs to yield meaningful details, trustworthy methods for color correction, sharpening, and background scattering removal are therefore required. These are especially difficult because of the complicated underwater environment, where turbidity, light absorption, and scattering—all of which can vary widely cause lower-quality photographs.

II. UNDERWATER IMAGE ENHANCEMENT METHODS

We approach the handling of specific problems in specific images using different algorithms. Many things are not perfect in the images taken underwater like the color attenuation, dark channels, intensity of the image, and adequate light to capture the image. We propose to use different algorithms for different problems to get the desired results. Underwater image enhancement is crucial to improve the visibility and quality of images in aquatic environments, where factors like attenuation, color distortion, and poor lighting significantly degrade image quality. Several methods and techniques are employed for underwater image enhancement.

A. Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization

CLAHE, or Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization, is an adaptive histogram equalization method aimed at mitigating noise amplification by constraining contrast enhancement. In CLAHE, the adjustment of contrast around a pixel value is determined by the slope of the transformation function. The histograms at this pixel value, linked to the image pixel values in the image, correspond to the slope of the original Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF). CLAHE effectively controls contrast enhancement by truncating or "clipping" the histogram at its peak value. CLAHE also constrains the slope of the CDF, which determines the slope of the transformation function. This restriction is influenced by factors such as the weight of the neighborhood window and the normalization of the histogram, particularly the clip limit. Typically, the resulting enhancement is capped at around three to four times the original values.

Fig. 1. Redistribution of Histogram

Opting to redistribute equal portions of the histogram that surpass the limit across the entire histogram bins could prove more efficient than outright discarding this portion. However, this redistribution process may cause some bins to exceed the clip limit, as depicted by the blue-shaded area in the figure. Consequently, this results in an effectively larger clip limit that deviates from the initially specified one, becoming more tailored to the specific characteristics of the image itself. The redistribution of excess can then be performed recursively until it becomes negligible.

```

1. DIVIDE THE INPUT IMAGE INTO NXN MATRIX OF SUB-IMAGES
2. FOR EACH SUB IMAGE DO:
  2.1 COMPUTE THE HISTOGRAM
  2.2 COMPUTE THE HIGH PEAK VALUE OF SUB-IMAGE
  2.3 CALCULATE THE NOMINAL CLIPPING LEVEL 0 TO HIGH
  2.4 FOR EACH GRAY LEVEL IN HISTOGRAM DO:
    A) IF THE HISTOGRAM BIN GREATER THAN CLIP LEVEL,CLIP THE HISTOGRAM
    TO NOMINAL CLIP LEVEL
    B) COLLECT THE NUBER OF PIXELS INT HE IMAGE THAT CAUSED THE HISTOGRAM
    TO EXCESS CLIP LEVEL
  2.5 DISTRIBUTE TE CLIPPED PIXEL UNIFORMELY IN ALL HISTOGRAM BINS
  TO OBTAIN NORMALIZED HISTOGRAM
  2.6 EQUALIZE THE HISTOGRAM TO OBTAIN CLIPPED HISTOGRAM EQUALIZE FOR
  SUB IMAGE
3. ADJUST THE BORDER PIXELS BY BILINEAR INTERPOLAIION
(DISTANCE WEIGHTED AVERAGE OF FOUR NEAREST PIXEL VALUES)
4. RETURN THE CLAHE IMAGE
  
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Fig. 2. CLAHE Algorithm

Fig. 3. Result Analysis of CLAHE

B. Rayleigh Stretching and Averaging

Underwater images typically contain both bright and dark regions. Employing global stretching to adjust the entire image can exacerbate overall image discrepancy. The brilliance of darker areas, it's necessary to increase the discrepancy within the image. Global stretching can indeed enhance the brilliance of bright areas, potentially resulting in over-improvement and loss of details in those regions. Similarly, applying global stretching to darker areas can lead to under-improvement, reducing image details. To address these effects, distinct image contrasts. The main aim is: one representing an under-enhanced image and the other an over-enhanced image. The following explanation briefly outlines how this system produces two images from a single channel in the RGB color model, with similar processes applied to other channels.

```

1.ALGORITHM RD
2.GET IMAGE FILE
3.GET height and width of the image
4.CALC RGB EQUALIZATION method with arguments height,width and the image itself
  a. Read the image as an numpy array
  b. Find the AVERAGE of each channel (i.e. (r,g,b)red,green,blue)
  c. Find the MAXIMUM value and the MINIMUM value in the array.
  d. Find the MEDIAN among the array
  e. Set the MINIMUM
  f. IF MINIMUM VALUE EQUALS AVERAGE of each channel i. Multiply A with each channel
  g. IF MAXIMUM VALUE EQUALS AVERAGE of each channel i. Multiply a with each channel
  h. Append those new r,g,b values m.Return it
5. CALC STRETCHING method with arguments the array
  a. Set the MAXIMUM and MINIMUM channel using
  b. For each pixel of the image(channel) do:
  c. Clip(i,j) = (int(channel(i,j) * (255 - 0) / (Max_channel - min_channel)) + 0.5).
  Return the image
6. CALC RAYLEIGH STRETCHING method with arguments the new image,height,width
  a. Find the upper and lower histogram stretching of each color channel (r,g,b)
  b. Create an numpy array of size of image and append the lower histogram
  stretching values of each channel
  c. Create an numpy array of size of image, and append the upper histogram
  stretching values of each channel
  d. Return both arrays
7. Sum these arrays and divide it by two and store it in sceneradiance
8. CALL HSV_STRETCHING and pass sceneradiance
  a. Read the height and width of this array
  b. Convert the image into hsv image from skimage library
  c. Do global stretching and save it to image library
  d. Convert it back into rgb using height and width and return it
  e. RETURN the image
9. CALL SCENERADIANCE method and pass this image
  a. Read the image
  b. Change the format into int
  c. RETURN the image
10. Output the image
  
```

Fig. 4. Rayleigh Algorithm

Fig. 5. Result Analysis of Rayleigh Algorithm.

The two resulting images are combined, and the average value between them is computed. Subsequently, the image, as well as the S (saturation) and V (value) factors of the HSV color model, are stretched within a dynamic range of 1 percent from the minimum to the maximum values. The final image is then obtained by conversion. Following these procedures for the corresponding channels, histograms with lower stretching are utilized to generate one image, while histograms with higher stretching are employed to create another image. This process yields two distinct images with varying contrasts: the lower region of the histogram produces an under-enhanced image, whereas the upper region generates an over-enhanced image.

C. Relative Global Histogram Stretching

In the RGB channels, it's crucial to acknowledge that the defined histogram may vary across different channels and images. Applying fixed values, such as 1,244, may lead to stretching extremes, resulting in either overstretching or under stretching specific color channels, thus compromising the original image details. It's imperative to adhere to the law of light propagation underwater, necessitating the application of contrast correction methods to rectify distorted images. Furthermore, when considering the distribution of histograms across color channels (i.e., RGB), observations from images captured in shallow water are noteworthy. In the majority of shallow-water images, the histogram for red light typically falls within the range of [50, 150], while both the green (G) and blue (B) channels are similarly concentrated within the range of [70, 210].

```

1.ALGORITHM RGHS
2.INPUT image file.
3.SET image as SceneRadiance.
4.CALCULATE STRETCHING on SceneRadiance
  a.GET image HEIGHT
  b.GET image WIDTH
  c.GET MAX_CHANNEL and MIN_CHANNEL
  d.PERFORM STRETCHING
  d1:img[i,j,k] = (img[i,j,k] - MIN_CHANNEL) * (255 - 0) / (MAX_CHANNEL - MIN_CHANNEL) + 0
  e.RETURN image
5.CALCULATE LABSTRETCHING on SceneRadiance
  a.GET image HEIGHT
  b.GET image WIDTH
  c.CONVERT RGB image TO CIELAB(L*a*b) COLOR SPACE
  d.SPLIT image TO "l", "a", "b" CHANNEL.
  d1.PERFORM STRETCHING ON "l"
  d2.PERFORM STRETCHING ON "a"
  d3.PERFORM STRETCHING ON "b"
  e.CONVERT image BACK TO RGB COLOR SPACE
  f.RETURN image
6.RETURN SceneRadiance AS FINAL OUTPUT.

```

Fig. 6. Result analysis of RGHS algorithm

.Fig. 7. Result analysis of RGHS Algorithm

This indicates that histogram stretching should consider all channels sensitively. The adaptive parameter acquired for the stretching range is derived from the histogram distribution of various images captured in shallow water. It's notable that the distribution across RGB channels resembles the Rayleigh distribution, which is a continuous probability distribution over positive random variables. Additionally, the distribution of channels exhibits normalcy, with the mode and midpoint almost identical. Therefore, we use the mode value as a reference point for determining the maximum and minimum intensity levels for individual decisions in histogram stretching. Underwater images are influenced by numerous factors, necessitating the mitigation of extreme pixel impact on relative global histogram stretching. Typically, the stretching range encompasses 0.1 percent to 99.9 percent of the histogram. However, if the histogram is not normally distributed, equal pixel removal becomes impractical. Thus, we partition intensity values into upper and lower percentages to calculate $I_{[min]}$ and perform histogram stretching accordingly.

D. Underwater Light Attenuation Prior

Light attenuation occurs when light intensity diminishes due to scattering and absorption by particles underwater during its transition between mediums. Restoring clarity to hazy underwater images is a task in computer vision. Unlike machines, humans can swiftly perceive scene depth in underwater images without additional information. Typically, the furthest point in the depth map resembling the original underwater scene is selected as the background light reference, as it reflects the weakening of sunlight underwater. Given that red light is absorbed more than green and blue light underwater, the largest intensity contrast between red and green-blue light is used to identify the background light in the image.

This contrast often serves as a candidate for background light determination. After examining various underwater images, we've identified a pattern known as the Underwater Light Attenuation Prior (ULAP). This pattern involves the relationship between the green-blue light intensity and the red light intensity within a pixel of the underwater image. Interestingly, ULAP shows a significant correlation with alterations in the depth of the scene.

```

1.ALGORITHM ULAP.
2.INPUT Image File.
3.CALCULATE DepthMap FOR Image.
  a.DepthMap = 0.3157954 * (MAX(img[:, :, 0], img[:, :, 1])) + (-0.90511117) * (img[:, :, 2])
  b.RETURN DepthMap.
4.PERFORM Globalstretching on DepthMap
5.CALCULATE AtomsphericLight
  a.PERFORM BacklightEstimation using Image and DepthMap.
  a.AtomsphericLight = BacklightEstimation * 255
6.GET MIN_DEPTH FROM Input_Image and AtomsphericLight
7.ESTIMATE TRANSMISSION FOR R, G, B CHANNEL INDIVIDUALLY.
  a.transmission_B = 0.97 ** (B * (DepthMap + MIN_DEPTH(img, AtomsphericLight)))
  b.transmission_G = 0.95 ** (B * (DepthMap + MIN_DEPTH(img, AtomsphericLight)))
  c.transmission_R = 0.83 ** (B * (DepthMap + MIN_DEPTH(img, AtomsphericLight)))
8.GET REFINED transmission.
  a.FILTER transmission_R, transmission_G, transmission_B WITH GUIDED FILTER
  b.RETURN REFINED transmission
9.CALCULATE SceneRadiance
  a.SceneRadiance = (img - AtomsphericLight) / transmission[:, :, 1] + AtomsphericLight
  b.Limit the transmittance between 0-255
  c.RETURN SceneRadiance
10.RETURN SceneRadiance AS FINAL OUTPUT.

```

Fig. 8. ULAP Algorithm.

Fig. 9. Result Analysis of ULAP Algorithm

The brightest pixel in an underwater image. The background light The candidate for background light is selected from the furthest point of the input image, specifically from the position of corresponding image. Opting for the furthest point ensures a more accurate estimation, as the determines presence of suspended particles can potentially obstruct valid estimation results.

E. Dark Channel Prior

The Dark Channel Prior (DCP) technique is highly a promising defogging method, as it consistently produces high-quality images with clear details, particularly in non-homogeneous regions. However, despite its effectiveness, the images recovered using this technique often exhibit block effects and color distortion, primarily attributed to the relatively large homogeneous patches.

```

1. ALGORITHM DCP
2. INPUT image file.
3. GET MINIMUM VALUED CHANNEL INTO ARRAY imgGrey
   IF IMAGE IS COLOURED AND TWO DIMENSIONAL THEN
     ACCEPT THE IMAGE
     GET THE GRAY SCALE IMAGE
   ELSE
     DISPLAY "bad image, no color found"
     DISCARD THE IMAGE and STOP ALGORITHM
4. GET DARK CHANNEL INTO VARIABLE imgDark From the greyscale image
   IF IMAGE IS IN GREYSCALE
     ACCEPT THE IMAGE
     GET THE DARK CHANNEL IMAGE
   ELSE
     DISPLAY "bad image shape, input image must be two dimensions"
     DISCARD THE IMAGE and STOP ALGORITHM
5. CALCULATE ATMOSPHERIC LIGHT
   SET SIZE, HEIGHT, WIDTH OF DARKCHANNEL
   GET atmosphericLight, res 0
   CALCULATE GREATEST INTENSITY VALUE FOR EACH CHANNEL
   RETURN atmosphericLight
6. CALCULATE TRANSMISSION
   CONVERT imgDark TO FLOAT
   transmission = 1 - omega * imgDark / atmosphericLight
   FILTER transmission WITH GUIDED FILTER
   CONVERT IMAGE TO FLOAT
   SET ARRAY sceneRadiance AS ZERO
7. CALCULATE SCENE RADIANCE
   sceneRadiance = (img - atmosphericLight) / transmission + atmosphericLight
   CONVERT sceneRadiance TO INTEGER TYPE
8. RETURN Image

```

Fig. 10. DCP Algorithm.

The two generated images are merged together, and the resulting underwater images exhibit a resemblance. The Dark Channel Prior (DCP) technique is widely adopted for repairing underwater pictures. On clear days, in natural images, the DCP channels predominantly display dark intensities when considering a square match within the image. Pixels derived from dark channels in hazy images often possess values significantly above zero. It's commonly observed that atmospheric light has a monochromatic nature.

Fig. 10. Result Analysis DCP Algorithm.

The efficiency of DCP in image de-hazing is evident through successful de-hazing outcomes achieved by various de-hazing algorithms. In underwater photography, some pixels display an intensity close to zero, possibly due to shadows. Despite the correctness of the assumption, the assumption of independent wavelengths leads to issues. In numerous real-world scenarios, the image is either entirely black or nearly devoid of information. In such cases, DCP may compromise the accuracy of transmission estimation. The medium's light absorption can cause the red channel to become almost negligible, even in shallow waters, rendering the data from unreliable.

F. Maximum Intensity Projection

In the realm of underwater cinematography, Carlevaris-Bianco introduced an efficient method called the MIP algorithm, which leverages the significant disparity in immersion among RGB wavelengths. Using this information, the algorithm calculates the scene by focusing on the contrast between the highest and lowest values of red channel intensity and prioritizing the blue-green channels to estimate medium transmission. Experimental trials have confirmed that the MIP algorithm is capable of generating rough depth maps of underwater scenes. Moreover, this algorithm is frequently utilized for estimating atmospheric light. To enhance the performance of the MIP algorithm, a refined version known as the New Optical Model (NOM) was introduced. The NOM offers an improved interpretation for computing atmospheric light, thereby enhancing the accuracy and effectiveness of the algorithm.

Fig. 12. MIP Algorithm

```

1.ALGORITHM MIP
2. INPUT image file.
3.CALCULATE DEPTH MAP
  GET MAXIMUM INTENSITY VALUE OF BLUE, GREEN CHANNEL
  GET MAXIMUM INTENSITY VALUE OF RED CHANNEL
  CALCULATE THE LARGEST DIFFERENCE OF MAXIMUM INTENSITY
  largestDiff=REDchannel INTENSITY- {BLUE, GREEN}channel INTENSITY
4.CALCULATE TRANSMISSION
  transmission = largestDiff + (1 - max_of(largestDiff))
5.CALCULATE REFINED TRANSMISSION
  REFINE transmission WITH GUIDED FILTER
6.CALCULATE ATMOSPHERIC LIGHT
  atmosphericLight IS PIXEL WITH HIGHEST INTENSITY VALUE IN
  REFINED TRANSMISSION
7.CALCULATE SCENE RADIANCE
  sceneRadiance=(img - AtmosphericLight) / transmission + AtmosphericLight
8.RETURN sceneRadiance

```

Fig. 13. Result Analysis of MIP Algorithm.

The assumption used was that the intensity of the R wavelength is relatively smaller than the intensity of the green-blue wavelengths within the area within the background. Zhao proposed a technique for the estimation of BL using MIP and DCP. The upper 0.1 percent of first, atmospheric light by selecting the pixels with the best difference. employing a mixed method in [80, 81], they picked only one flat area of the background using a quad-tree, then selected the upper from the chosen region. Ambient light. Because the atmospheric light within the background is blurred, we use MIP to truly get the simplest atmospheric light and acquire the ultimate scene radiance with maximum intensity.

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